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ACADEMIC SUCCESS OF FIRST-YEAR-STUDENTS – WHAT'S THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN MECHANICAL AND CIVIL ENGINEERING STUDENTS?

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ABSTRACT

First-year students of mechanical and civil engineering show a high degree of heterogeneity. The purpose of the present study is to investigate the two engineering courses with regard to which characteristics at the beginning of the studies are more likely leading to academic success. Different selected variables are examined, in terms of demographic variables, special knowledge (mathematics and engineering mechanics) and academic success. It can be shown that demographic variables make a significant difference and have a corresponding impact on the person ability achieved in the applied knowledge tests by the students of both engineering courses at the beginning and end of the first semester.

1 INTRODUCTION

A catchphrase that is currently frequently used in the discourse about the reform of the German higher education system is heterogeneity. In general, heterogeneity is understood as a temporary, attributed inconsistency that exists between members or a part of members of a specific group based on one or more criteria [1]. The student body is becoming increasingly heterogeneous [2, 3]. This raises concerns that it can become more and more difficult to design large lectures / courses that do justice to (almost) everyone [1, 4]. It can be assumed that certain characteristics of the students correlate with their performance and therefore increasing diversity in those characteristics can also result in an increasing heterogeneity of their performance.

The University of Duisburg-Essen [UDE] (Germany – North Rhine-Westfalia) is characterized by a high degree of heterogeneity among its students. This university is in the Ruhr region, where the students often come from low-income and / or poorly educated social classes, and usually have an immigration background. On the one hand this large group of students has a high affinity for scientific and technical subjects, on the other hand the students of this group have particular problems during their studies. They represent a special risk group with regard to their academic success and even drop out of university down the road [5]. An empirical study at the UDE found out that gender, a non-academic family educational background, a history of immigration, a lack of a vocational qualification and a below-average higher education entrance [HEE] grade (Abitur) are among the factors that delay the completion of the study and also increase the risk of student drop-out [6, 7].

This paper examines the current state of the two most strongly represented engineering courses at the UDE [8] – mechanical engineering [ME] and civil engineering [CE] – based on empirical findings. Various socio-demographic characteristics and knowledge tests were selected for the present analysis. In the following, the background of these factors and - initially purely descriptive - their characteristics in both engineering courses are presented.

2 METHODOLOGY

Demographic variables like age, gender, HEE grade, type of HEE acquisition and the corresponding location, participation of mathematics and physics courses at the upper school level, delay before begin of the studies, immigration, family educational background and vocational education were recorded as part of a questionnaire. This demographic questionnaire was completed subject-independent by all studied first-year students at the beginning of the first semester [MP1].

The scales for recording the subject-related study prerequisites (previous knowledge) and the course performance (special knowledge) were also applied as paper and pencil tests at the beginning [MP1] and at the end of the first semester [MP2]. The test (multiple-choice-single-select format) contains mathematic and engineering mechanics [EM] items from the item pool by Dammann & Lang [9] – both subjects are considered to be of central importance for the two engineering courses [10]. These tests are used in order to have an objective measure that reflects the special knowledge as part of the students academic success in the respective courses. The tests are scaled using the 1-PL-IRT model (Rasch). The tests are showing satisfactory reliabilities and separations for MP1 (WLE reliability = .77, EAP reliability = .78), therefore the person ability (WLE) can be used for the subsequent analyzes.

In order to be able to compare the WLE and to calculate the subject-specific increase in knowledge, the item difficulties at MP2 (special knowledge) are fixed to the values of the IRT-scaling at MP1 (previous knowledge). The calculation of the model for MP2 with fixed item difficulties also shows satisfactory parameters (WLE reliability = .84, EAP reliability = .84).

3 RESULTS

3.1 Heterogeneity of both engineering courses

The presentation of the results initially shows basic demographic characteristics of the ME and CE students. These characteristics reflect their fundamental heterogeneity. Also the basic variables are characterized by the fact that they are constant over time e.g. age, gender, HEE (grade, type of acquisition, corresponding location and participation of mathematics and physics courses) and family educational background. The cognitive competence and the personality of the students are also counted as exogenous student capital.

By looking at the individual characteristics, first insights into the specifics of first-year students can be found. For this purpose, socio-demographic data is used, which can provide information about the heterogeneity of the considered groups.

The applied questionnaire was answered by 88 ME and 290 CE students. The descriptive analysis of the data shows an average age of 20.1 years for ME and 20.7 years for CE students; the two groups do not differ significantly in average age.

The gender distribution of ME students is 81.6 % men and 18.4 % women, in contrast the distribution among CE students is 67.1 % men and 37.9 % women. This means that the gender distribution of the two groups differs significantly from one another ($n_{ME} = 87$, $n_{CE} = 289$, $\chi^2(1) = 6.74$, $p = .009$, Cramers $V = .134$). The share of women in the field of CE is already relatively high for an engineering study course, generally the numbers vary between 12 and 19 % [11].

The surveyed ME students achieved an average HEE grade of 2.55, while the CE students achieved a significantly inferior average HEE grade of 2.81 ($n_{ME} = 86$, $n_{CE} = 256$, $t(340) = -3.67$, $p = .000$).

Significant differences can also be observed in the acquisition type of the HEE ($n_{ME} = 89$, $n_{CE} = 288$, $\chi^2(4) = 15.58$, $p = .004$, Cramers $V = .203$). While 64.0 % of the ME students have obtained their HEE at a secondary school (Gymnasium), 20.2 % obtained their HEE at a comprehensive school (Gesamtschule). Compared to the ME students, 56.6 % of the CE students obtained their HEE at a secondary school, while 29.2 % obtained it at a comprehensive school.

The remaining students of both groups obtained their HEE at a vocational college, by second-chance education or miscellaneous. Since the curricula in the individual school types differ in the course content, it cannot be assumed that the level of knowledge at the beginning of the course is homogeneous.

The HEE was acquired from 96.3 % of ME students in North Rhine-Westfalia; only three students acquired it in another federal state. No ME student has attained the HEE abroad. 87.5 % of the CE students acquired their HEE in North Rhine-Westfalia, six students in another federal state. 10.4 % of the CE students attained their HEE abroad, the majority of them in Syria ($n_{ME} = 81$, $n_{CE} = 289$, Fisher-Test: 16.27, $p = .002$).

There are no significant differences in the choice of basic or advanced mathematics courses at the upper school level. Almost a 50 % / 50 % (basic / advanced) distribution

can be determined for the CE students and a 35 % / 65 % distribution for the ME students. In contrast, significant differences can be identified in the choice of the physics courses. On the one hand, 35 % of the ME students chose the basic and 25 % the advanced physics courses at the upper school level. On the other hand, 32 % of the CE students chose the basic and 8 % the advanced course. In contrast it is striking that 40 % of the ME and almost 60% of CE students have never attended a physics course at the upper school level ($n_{ME} = 84$, $n_{CE} = 234$, $\chi^2(2) = 18.55$, $p = .000$, Cramers $V = .242$).

In addition to the acquired knowledge and skills that enable students to study, the delay in secondary education also plays a role, as Henn and Polaczek [12] have already noted. The ME students who started their studies in the winter semester 2018/19 received their HEE 1.5 years before starting their studies. The CE students who obtained their HEE 1.9 years before starting their studies are showing no significantly larger time delay regarding the transition from school to higher education.

The immigration background of the students was recorded in the form of the native language. When asked whether German is their mother tongue, 75.3 % of ME students agreed. In the cohort surveyed, therefore 24.7 % do not speak German as their first language. On a three-level scale with regard to their German language skills, 69.4 % of the non-native speakers evaluate their German language skills as “very good”, 27.8 % as “good”, while just 2.8 % choose the lowest level “basic knowledge”. Regarding the distribution of whether German is the mother tongue, there are significant differences relating to the CE students ($n_{ME} = 89$, $n_{CE} = 290$, $\chi^2(1) = 15.02$, $p = .000$, Cramers $V = .199$). Just 52.1 % of the CE students speak German as their native language, corresponding 47.9 % are not speaking German as their mother tongue. Here, 66.2 % of the non-native speakers state that their German language skills are “very good”, 33.1 % as “good”, while here, too, the lowest level “basic knowledge” is chosen by 0.7 %.

The family educational background is characterized by a four-stage classification according to the concept by the DZHW [13]. The characteristics of the vocational education of the father and mother of the students are divided according to the following classification: low = one parent has a vocational (non-academic) degree, average = both parents have a vocational (non-academic) degree, enhanced = one parent has an academic degree, high = both parents have an academic degree. The division according to the family educational background shows no significant differences in the distribution of ME and CE students. As shown in Fig. 1 a comparison with the results of the 21st social survey (universities from 2016) of the DZHW [13] shows that a larger share of the cohort of CE students have a low or average family educational background (almost 60%) compared to the 21st social survey (42%) [13]. Accordingly, the share of enhanced or high family educational background is lower. In contrast, the ME students almost exactly achieve the mentioned values of the DZHW study [13].

Fig. 1: Bar chart of the family educational background distribution

8% of the total cohort of ME students have completed a vocational education before starting their studies, of which 33 % have similar content in their vocational education related to their ME studies. 10.3 % of the CE students have already completed a vocational education before starting their studies, with 75.9 % a significantly higher share has similar content in their vocational education related to their CE studies ($n_{ME} = 2$, $n_{CE} = 22$, $\chi^2(1) = 4.17$, $p = .041$, Cramers $V = .345$). 13.7 % of ME students already have study experience, there is no significant difference regarding CE students with also 13.7 %.

After the heterogeneity of the students has been highlighted in this chapter, it should be examined whether the students also differ in terms of their average person ability in the knowledge test, and whether there are correlations between the average personal ability and the mentioned demographic variables.

3.2 Relation between person ability and demographic variables

Students from both study courses start with similar average person abilities regarding their previous knowledge (MP1). For the special knowledge (MP2) it can be seen that the students of CE performed significantly better in these tests ($n_{ME} = 56$, $n_{CE} = 58$, $t(112) = -.279$, $p = .000$) (Fig. 2).

The average person ability regarding previous knowledge (MP1) and special knowledge (MP2) were compared with one another in order to check the students increase in knowledge and thus their academic success (Fig. 2). At MP2, a large number of the students no longer participated in the study, so the number of participants dropped noticeably. To test the extent to which these average values differ from one another, t-tests were calculated. There is a significant difference in the increase in special knowledge for ME ($n_{ME} = 52$, $t(51) = -6.16$, $p = .000$) and CE students ($n_{CE} = 46$, $t(45) = -9.68$, $p = .000$).

Fig. 2: Error bars of the average person ability for the ME and CE students at MP1 and MP2

In the following, correlation analyzes are used to examine the correlations that emerge for ME and CE students between the average person ability achieved in the knowledge tests at both measuring points and some of the recorded demographic variables. Table 1 shows the correlation of the average personal ability and the HEE grade. All correlations are negative medium strong and highly significant.

Table 1. Correlation between average person ability for the ME and CE students and the HEE grade

		HEE grade	
		ME	CE
average person ability	MP1	-.308**	-.356**
	MP2	-.383**	-.385**

** < .001

For a closer examination the HEE grades were grouped – according to the grading in Germany – (A = 1.0 - 1.4, B = 1.5 - 2.4, C = 2.5 - 3.4, D = 3.5 - 4.0) and considered in relation to the average person ability in previous and special knowledge (Fig. 3). Generally strong characteristic error bars indicate a low n within the group.

It is clear that the person ability of all students improves in both engineering courses, regardless of the HEE grade. However, you can see that students with a worse HEE grade are not in the position to close the gap to the students with better HEE grades. Anyhow, the CE students always achieve a better person ability than the ME students. It must be emphasized that for the CE students (grouped grade D) at MP2 the trend is not the same as for the other grouped grades, this could be justified by the fact that this group consists of only 2 students.

Fig. 3: Error bars of the average person ability for the ME and CE students at MP1 and MP2 divided by the HEE grade

When choosing a course at the upper school level, the subject mathematics was divided into students who have attended a basic course or an advanced course (Fig. 4). The correlation coefficients between average person ability and the choice of course in mathematics are shown in Table 2. For ME and CE students at MP1 and MP2, there is a correlation between average person ability and the choice of the mathematics course. This correlation is also evident for both student groups at MP2. The same division into basic course and advanced course was also made for the school subject physics, but here is also the possibility of not choosing the subject at all. For the ME students, a correlation can be shown for the average person ability of MP1 and MP2. A correlation regarding the CE students is just existent for the average person ability at MP1 (Table 2).

Table 2. Correlation between average person ability for the ME and CE students and the subjects mathematics and physics

		mathematics		physics	
		ME	CE	ME	CE
average person ability	MP1	.326**	.304**	.447**	.260**
	MP2	.294*	.345*	.411**	

** < .001, * < .005

Fig. 4: Error bars of the average person ability for the ME and CE students at MP1 and MP2 divided by the course type of mathematics and physics at upper school level

The immigration history also has a significant impact on the person ability of individual students. For ME students, there is a correlation between the average person ability and their native language with a negative effect ($r = -.240$, $p < 0.028$) at MP1 (Table 3). For CE students only a correlation exists between the average person ability at MP1 and the native language.

Table 3. Correlation between average person ability for the ME and CE students and the native language

		native language	
		ME	CE
average person ability	MP1	-.240*	-.308**
	MP2	-.273*	

** < .001, * < .005

The family educational background also provides information about the person ability (Fig. 4). With increasing family educational background, the average person ability at MP1 for both study courses increases. No significant correlation can be shown both engineering courses at MP2.

Fig. 5: Error bars of the average person ability for the ME and CE students at MP1 and MP2 divided by the family educational background

4 SUMMARY

The first-year students of ME and CE at the UDE are characterized by great heterogeneity, as the study carried out with regard to school education, immigration background and vocational education. The differences in vocational education affect only a very small part of the overall cohort. The school education, i.e. the acquisition of the HEE differs mainly in the achieved HEE grade and in the type of school in which the HEE was acquired. Accordingly, more than a third of the students acquired the HEE at a comprehensive school or through vocational education. The courses at the upper school level are also of interest. While for the ME students the choice between basic and advanced course was almost the same in mathematics, almost 40% did not participate in the courses of physics at all (60 % of the CE students), although it is important for engineering studies.

Both student groups showed significant correlations between the average person ability – both in terms of previous (MP1) and special knowledge (MP2) – and the HEE, the choice of courses in mathematics and physics, the native language and the vocational education.

Based on these findings, support measures for students in the preliminary and / or introductory phase of their studies should now be developed by means of a suitable diagnostic option.

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